

A Model Predictive Control framework for Smart Predictive Digital Twins in Water Supply Systems

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Abstract: Water utilities face new challenges in adapting to the energy transition, marked by the rise of renewable generation, flexible loads and more dynamic energy markets. This transition also offers opportunities for more sustainable water supply operational management. Recently, Model Predictive Control (MPC) has gained interest in water supply system (WSS) management due to its ability to incorporate forecasting, such as water demand and renewable generation, into real-time optimal control operations; yet its adoption within the water sector remains limited and validation is lacking. This paper presents an MPC framework to minimize energy costs in WSS, integrating features like time-differentiated energy prices, on-site renewable generation, and energy storage systems. Validation on a real-world network demonstrates significant potential savings, highlighting the role of MPC in assisting real-time decision-making for efficient operation of water utilities contributing to the energy transition.

Keywords: Model predictive Control; Smart Predictive Digital Twins; Water Supply Systems.

Traditionally, water supply and power systems have been designed and operated as two uncoupled systems. However, they are intrinsically linked through a co-dependent and complex relation of mutual exchange of resources often referred to as the Water-Energy Nexus [1, 2]. Misunderstanding the interdependence between water and energy can lead to overuse and mismanagement of these resources. Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of the Water-Energy Nexus is essential for sustainable resource management. This Nexus has been recognized as one of the most pressing and critical multidisciplinary challenges that power and water utilities must address in the forthcoming years [1, 3].

Water supply systems (WSS) are energy-intensive infrastructures encompassing water storage tanks and pumping systems to deliver water to consumers. Enhancing WSS operational efficiency is essential given the current challenges facing the water sector, especially ensuring sustainable water for everyone, rising energy costs, dynamic energy pricing, as well as aging infrastructure. However, recent trends offer new opportunities for water utilities to play a key role in the power sector by contributing to demand-side management (DSM). Water utilities can significantly reduce their energy costs by participating in demand response (DR) programs leveraged by their flexibility in scheduling pumping operations, particularly with the adoption of dynamic energy tariffs in smart grids. Additionally, current investments in efficient equipment, on-site renewable energy sources (RES), use of energy storage systems and optimized load management through pumping schedules mitigate exposure to energy price fluctuations and can further benefit both water and power utilities in terms of cost savings, operational efficiency, and grid stability.

Although the opportunities brought by the energy transition for water utilities are becoming recognized, the growing complexity of real-time resource management, including water demand, tank storage, on-site RES, shiftable pumping loads, electric batteries, and energy participation in DR programs, makes it increasingly difficult for WSS operational teams to manage efficiently. This complexity arises due to the variability of the resources and is further exacerbated when operational decision-making must be made dynamically in near real-time, which requires advanced decision-support tools. So, a major challenge lies in finding operational control strategies that address real-time WSS management from an integrated resource perspective, while meeting consumers' water demand. To the author's knowledge, no study has comprehensively addressed the demand-side flexibility of WSS operation with an integrated resource management approach aimed at reducing energy costs.

Figure 1.1 WSS operations teams struggle with integrated resource management in the face of energy transition opportunities.

This work develops and implements innovative solutions to tackle the growing complexity of near real-time resource management in WSS, particularly on the bulk supply side due to its high energy consumption. The research focuses on efficient DSM strategies while considering the underlying physical and operational constraints. The work aims to demonstrate how water utilities can reduce operational costs by promoting integrated resource management and contributing to more decarbonized power systems by providing flexibility in grid stress moments.

MPC has gained interest in WSS management due to its ability to incorporate forecasting, such as water demand and renewable generation, into real-time optimal control operations. Yet, its adoption into the water sector remains limited. For this purpose, a Model Predictive Control (MPC) framework was developed, incorporating digital twins referred to as predictor models for WSS hydraulic behavior and electric battery dynamics, combined with nonlinear optimization techniques. This approach enables the resolution of complex optimization problems within feasible computational timeframes, yielding practical and effective solutions.

Unlike previous studies, which often consider only time-of-use energy tariffs, this framework developed encompasses several resources and equipment to be managed: (i) water demand, (ii) variable-speed pumps (VSP), (iii) water storage tanks, (iv) power grid energy supply with real-time pricing, (v) on-site renewable generation, and (vi) electric batteries. The framework integrates a wide range of energy resources

and interactions with the power grid, facilitating real-time electricity transactions (buying and selling) tailored to specific needs. To the authors' knowledge, no existing literature offers such a comprehensive model supporting real-time WSS operation.

Figure 1.2 Model Predictive Control adopted in this work to promote integrated resource management in WSS operation.

The validation of the proposed methodology was conducted using a real-world WSS. The MPC demonstrated superior cost-efficient operation results (both in terms of pumps and battery utilization) reducing the energy cost by 32% compared to a standard approach, where pump control is based on trigger setpoints defined by the water utility water tank levels and provided flexibility benefits to the power grid. Compared to conventional practices, this framework enabled peak power reductions exceeding 40% and achieved flexibility factors above 55%, underscoring the significant role of WSS in providing flexibility to the grid.

Operation	Energy Cost (€)	Energy cost red* (%)	Avg. SE (kWh/m ³)	SE red* (%)	Avg. SEC (€/m ³)	SEC red* (%)	Flexibility Factor
Standard	1560.28	-	1.104	-	0.076	-	
Optimal	1064.26	31.79	1.083	1.89	0.062	18.66	> 0.58

*Reduction

Despite the growing recognition of these opportunities within water utilities, their traditional design and operation practices are not aligned with the evolving energy market and a future built on clean energy. The misalignment is exacerbated by challenges faced by the water sector, including greater operational complexity in WSS due to expanding resources to manage, lack of real-time decision support tools to cope with this increased complexity, and an aging workforce leading to a loss of operational knowledge. By integrating diverse resources into WSS operational management, the presented framework supports water utilities in their energy transition, contributing to both energy and cost reductions. It also offers insights into developing cross-sectoral water-energy strategies, ensuring flexible power system operations without compromising WSS performance.

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